

Fusion for Intelligent Decision-support in Ophthalmology Challenge: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Fusion for Intelligent Decision-support in Ophthalmology Challenge

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

FIDO Challenge

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Ophthalmic surgery demands precise real-time image guidance to navigate complex tool maneuvers and perform delicate tissue manipulation. This challenge focuses on the development of multimodal AI-driven decision-support systems, uniting clinical experts with technical researchers to foster innovation in this critical field. Specifically, we will explore and discuss how real-time intraoperative multimodal image fusion can significantly enhance holistic surgical scene understanding, thereby delivering added clinical value. This, in particular, addresses the integration of complementary imaging modalities, including surgical microscope imaging, providing a wide-field contextual view, and intraoperative Optical Coherence Tomography (iOCT), which delivers high-resolution cross-sectional anatomical details. This fusion of multimodal data is essential for accurate surgical tool tracking, tissue state analysis, and understanding surgical phase.

Integrating such advanced multimodal data fusion solutions into clinical practice has so far been limited by the access to the required annotated and registered data sets. To tackle this, we provide highly specialized and tailored synthetic data that allows the development of solutions that demonstrate the potential of surgical assistance systems for complex, dynamic surgical procedures. To facilitate methodology development and benchmarking, the challenge is based on synthetic multimodal retina-surgery video datasets with full ground truth information. Participants can engage in sub-challenges categorized into two main tracks: Surgical instrument localization and multimodal registration between iOCT and microscope imaging.

The challenge day will include keynote presentations on the latest advancements in multimodal imaging, image processing, intuitive surgical visualization, and decision-support systems that enhance precision in interventional ophthalmology. Technical keynotes are complemented by clinical keynotes from experienced surgical specialists, underscoring the importance of systematic methodological design in translating clinical expertise into effective

technical systems and in bridging the domain gap between medical specialists and medical imaging researchers. In addition to invited keynotes, the challenge welcomes participants interested in working with multimodal surgical data and encourages the submission and presentation of their novel approaches developed using the provided synthetic dataset.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Multimodal data fusion, Real-time intraoperative decision support in Ophthalmology, Surgical Tool Detection, Contrastive Learning

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

In ophthalmic surgery, the integration of new imaging modalities such as intraoperative OCT (iOCT) has improved the ability to sense and monitor the surgical environment. However, current clinical practice, as well as currently proposed technical solutions, typically rely on only one imaging modality at a time: either iOCT or fundus microscope imaging, despite each providing complementary information. While multimodal data fusion could enable more holistic surgical scene understanding, the potential of using both modalities simultaneously to deliver holistic intraoperative feedback remains largely unexplored, primarily due to the lack of available multimodal datasets.

In the absence of such datasets containing both fundus images and iOCT data, including even unlabeled data, SynthesEyes, the winner of the MICCAI Medical Valley Challenge 2025, has partnered with Carl Zeiss Meditec AG, a leader in ophthalmic imaging and surgery, to collect and release a multimodal dataset and introduce it through this challenge. This initiative represents the first systematic effort to enable researchers to explore multimodal data fusion, highlighting the opportunities that arise when they are used together rather than independently.

The challenge is further designed to foster close collaboration between researchers and surgeons, giving participants direct exposure to medical opinion leaders and their clinical needs. By promoting this interaction, the challenge aims to guide future research directions and encourage the community to advance toward the joint use of fundus imaging and iOCT in ophthalmic surgery.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The challenge consists of two parallel scenarios:

A: Surgical instrument keypoints localization

B: Intraoperative iOCT registration

Scenario A:

In vitreoretinal surgery, accurate localization of surgical instruments and estimation of the distance between the tool and retinal tissue are critical for safe and precise manipulation. Surgeons traditionally infer this distance from visual cues in fundus images, such as the tool's shadow on the retina. However, for real-time automated decision support and robotic assistance, a more reliable and quantitative estimation is required.

In this scenario, the task focuses on surgical tool keypoint detection in fundus images and tool-tissue distance estimation, leveraging both fundus and intraoperative OCT (iOCT) data. Fundus images provide a wide-field view and contextual information, while iOCT offers localized cross-sectional and micrometer resolution depth information that is essential for understanding tool-tissue relationships. Although iOCT has inherent advantages for distance estimation, it may not be available in all frames due to device limitations or acquisition constraints. Therefore, a robust approach must be capable of learning from both modalities during training, while remaining effective during inference and remain robust to data corruption of a single modality.

Ground-truth tool-tissue distances and tool keypoints are provided for training and evaluation. Participants are encouraged to develop multimodal or contrastive learning approaches that exploit complementary information from iOCT and fundus imaging to improve distance estimation accuracy and tool localization. This scenario explicitly promotes multimodal data fusion methods and applications while reflecting realistic intraoperative conditions. Evaluation also involves 100 real-world data samples to test how well models handle domain shifts and the clinical impact of the models.

Scenario B:

A common challenge in perceptual visualization of multimodal data, multi-modal data fusion and robotic task autonomy is estimating the transformation between different imaging modalities. Although imaging systems typically provide this information internally, it can sometimes be inaccurate due to factors such as outdated or incorrect calibrations. Accurately estimating the transformation is a fundamental step for precise multimodal integration, surgical guidance, and automated or robotic interventions. In this scenario, both iOCT and fundus images are provided along with the ground truth transformation between them, and the goal is to develop an algorithm capable of accurately estimating this transformation. Additionally, similar to scenario A, a set of real-world cases is provided in the test set to evaluate the algorithm's performance and robustness under clinical conditions.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

Following the Area Chair's recommendation and discussions with the workshop organizers, we have scheduled the challenge to take place during the afternoon session in conjunction with the OMIA13 Workshop and GAVE Challenge (CMT IDs 269 and 220).

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The challenge session will open with a keynote lecture by a vitreoretinal surgeon, followed by an interdisciplinary panel featuring leading experts from academia, industry, and clinical practice. Together, they will explore the future of multimodal imaging, its clinical and technological applications, and the pivotal role of researchers in driving progress in this area.

Selected top teams will then showcase their innovative approaches and results, highlighting state-of-the-art developments in surgical guidance and multimodal data analysis.

The session will conclude with a short award ceremony.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We estimate that 30–60 teams will participate in the challenge, based on trends observed in comparable challenges and the overall growth trajectory of MICCAI. This estimate is informed by the community's increasing interest in multimodal data fusion and by participation rates in previous ophthalmology workshops (OMIA). In addition, by introducing this novel multimodal dataset, the challenge may attract researchers who have not previously worked in ophthalmology but are interested in multimodal image processing, providing them with an opportunity to explore a new domain, test innovative ideas, and engage with a unique and challenging dataset.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

The challenge organizers will coordinate a joint publication summarizing the results within six months of the challenge's conclusion. This manuscript will present the methods of the winners from each scenario, though the organizing committee may also include noteworthy approaches from non-winning teams. Each team may have an unlimited number of participants but must nominate up to two main contributors to be listed as co-authors. All co-authors are required to approve the final manuscript, and the order of authorship will be determined by the organizers. After this publication, participating teams are welcome to publish their individual results, citing the official FIDO Challenge manuscript.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get

the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be conducted entirely online, so no on-site computing environment will be needed. For the talks and panel sessions, a basic setup with a projector, speakers, and a microphone are sufficient.

TASK 1: Surgical instrument keypoints spatial localisation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Surgical instrument keypoint detection and spatial localisation are fundamental yet still challenging tasks in computer-aided surgery and real-time decision-support systems, with wide applications ranging from surgical video analysis to robotic automation. In vitreoretinal surgery, these tasks have been commonly studied; however, existing approaches are typically single-modality and often lack the level of precision required for such delicate procedures. Vitreoretinal surgery requires micrometer precision, where even minor inaccuracies can lead to significant clinical consequences.

Conventional methods primarily rely on fundus video images and CNN-based approaches to detect surgical instruments keypoints on fundus images, but these methods often struggle to generalize and to achieve sufficient accuracy. In this task, leveraging the multimodal nature of the dataset, researchers are encouraged to explore how an additional imaging modality, intraoperative OCT, which provides high-resolution three-dimensional anatomical information over a smaller region of interest, can be used to enhance tool keypoints detection in fundus video. Moreover, the additional imaging modality is leveraged to estimate tool-tissue distance, thereby extending conventional 2D keypoint detection into accurate spatial (pseudo-3D) localization of the surgical instrument relative to retinal tissue.

The goal is to achieve substantially improved precision while maintaining real-time performance, enabling more reliable intraoperative guidance.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multi-modal image fusion, keypoint detection, spatial localisation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Shervin Dehghani (1),

Michael Sommersperger (1),

Christian Kungel (3),

Ghazal Ghazaei (2, 4),

Hendrik Burwinkel (3),

Koorosh Faridpooya (5)

Nassir Navab (4)

-

(1) SynthesEyes GmbH, Munich, DE

(2) Corporate Research and Technology, Carl Zeiss AG, Munich, DE

(3) Advanced Development, Carl Zeiss Meditec AG, Munich, DE

(4) Chair of Computer Aided Medical Procedures (CAMP), Technical University of Munich (TUM)

(5) Rotterdam Eye Hospital, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Shervin Dehghani (SynthesEyes GmbH)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Clinicians have been closely involved in the design of the challenge to assess whether the learned patterns align with how human surgeons perceive and reason about surgical tool positioning. In addition to quantitative evaluation, clinicians will remain actively involved during the review of submitted methods, providing expert insight to help interpret and validate the underlying logic and clinical applicability of novel approaches.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention 2026 (MICCAI)

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Will be hosted on codabench.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

All relevant information about the challenge, including key details such as deadlines, submission instructions, and evaluation criteria, along with all relevant links, will be made available on the official challenge website. This website is hosted by SynthesEyes GmbH and will serve as the central hub for participants to stay updated on all aspects of the challenge.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

There are no restrictions on the data that can be used for training. While the necessary training data will be provided and the evaluation dataset will be similar in nature, researchers are allowed to leverage additional publicly available datasets and pre-trained models. Any such additional data or models used must be clearly documented, specifying which datasets and pre-trained networks were incorporated into the training process.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top-performing team in the qualitative evaluation and the team with the most innovative or impactful approach will receive awards. The award amounts will be announced later.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top performing team of the task will be announced publicly on the challenge website.

Moreover, the team with the most innovative or impactful approach for the task will be announced publicly on the challenge website.

All these teams will be listed as co-authors in the final manuscript, and have the opportunity to present their method on the challenge day.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The challenge organizers will coordinate a joint publication summarizing the results of the challenge, to be completed within six months after the challenge concludes. This manuscript will highlight both the best-performing team based on qualitative evaluation per task and the team with the most impactful or innovative approach (these could be the same team, as determined by the organizing committee). All participating teams are required to provide detailed information about their methods and, if applicable, their training code. While each team may include an unlimited number of participants, each team should introduce up to two main contributors to be listed as co-authors on the final manuscript. All co-authors must contribute to drafting and revising the manuscript, provide necessary information, critically assess important intellectual content, and give final approval for the version to be published. The final authorship order will be determined by the challenge organizers. After the joint publication, teams are welcome to publish their individual results separately, provided they cite the official FIDO Challenge manuscript.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Model submission and automatic evaluation will be managed through Codabench, providing a streamlined and standardized platform for participants to submit their models and receive evaluation results efficiently. The submission instructions, including a detailed specification of the exact model output format, will be published on Codabench and the corresponding challenge website, which is hosted by SynthesEyes GmbH. By following the specified model output format, participants can ensure that their submitted model's output is successfully processed by the evaluation code on the Codabench platform.

Furthermore, we will provide Python code for data loading to ensure that all participants start with a consistent and standardized input for training and running their models. We provide a platform for participants to verify the technical functionality of their submitted Docker containers. For the evaluation of the algorithms, only the last submitted version will be considered. An evaluation on the test data will only be performed once per team to prevent iterative adaptation to the test data.

All submissions will require inference to be possible on a single NVIDIA GPU (<24 GB). In addition, a real-time inference constraint will be enforced, and the inference time on the evaluation set will be restricted accordingly. The exact latency thresholds and the specific GPU model used for evaluation will be specified at the time of dataset release.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Teams will receive training data for model development. To help participants ensure and independently verify that their submission is fundamentally correct, we have implemented the following provisions. Participants will be given instructions to self-evaluate their code as a sanity check before the submission. We will also make available the scripts that run on the evaluation server after submission (including Python code for computing the specified

evaluation metrics). All necessary code for the challenge will be provided to participants via GitHub, ensuring easy access. Participants can use these scripts, together with the public Docker image and the validation set (i.e. a self-defined part of the provided local training data), to perform sanity checks locally. This procedure will enable participants to confirm that their solutions function as intended. Due to the expected long runtime requirements of the submitted models and limited computational resources.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Registration Period: April 1 - June 30, 2026
 - Dataset Release: April 7, 2026
 - Model Submission Period: June 1 – July 31, 2026
 - Finalists Announcement: August 31, 2026
 - Final Submission Date: September 1, 2026
 - Results Announcement: Challenge Day, October 4 and 8, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Not applicable to our dataset, since it is purely synthetic. While the evaluation phase incorporates real-world data to test for domain shift, this specific subset will remain private and will not be released for public distribution.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide the corresponding links for the data loaders and evaluation code to participants of the challenge. This release is planned for the beginning of May 2026.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The challenge organizers will ensure that the participants' source code and model weights remain confidential and will not be disclosed publicly during the evaluation phase. After the challenge is finished, training and inference code from selected participating teams with leading scores will be made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge is funded by Carl Zeiss Meditec AG and SynthesEyes GmbH. To ensure fairness, only designated members of the organizing team will have access to the test case labels, and these labels will remain confidential until the evaluation phase is complete. No other participants or affiliated parties have access to these labels prior to the release of the final results.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training

- Cross-phase

Surgery, Assistance, Intervention planning, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Localization, Tracking

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this challenge consists of patients undergoing retinal surgery, a class of highly delicate ophthalmic procedures that rely on precise intraoperative visualization and tool-tissue interaction. Retinal surgery is performed across a broad and diverse patient population, including individuals of different ages, sexes, and ethnic backgrounds.

Patients within the target cohort may present with varying degrees of disease severity, anatomical variability, and surgical complexity, all of which can influence surgical strategy and outcomes. The final biomedical application of this challenge aims to support surgeons during real-world retinal interventions through enhanced intraoperative decision support based on multimodal imaging, including fundus microscope imaging and intraoperative OCT.

While the primary focus of this challenge is retinal surgery, the proposed methodologies are designed to be generalizable and may be extended to other forms of ophthalmic surgery, such as cataract surgery or additional anterior and posterior segment procedures, where multimodal intraoperative imaging is used. As such, the target

cohort conceptually includes a broader ophthalmic surgical population that could benefit from multimodal image fusion and AI-assisted guidance in future clinical applications.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of synthetic multimodal retinal surgery data generated by SynthesEyes GmbH. The dataset is fully synthetic and does not originate from direct intraoperative recordings; instead, it is created based on fully anonymised and synthetically recreated patient cases and surgical scenarios provided by partner university clinics. These clinical cases serve as the foundation for realistically modeling retinal anatomy, surgical tools, and intraoperative dynamics across imaging modalities.

By using a synthetic dataset, the challenge avoids patient privacy concerns while enabling controlled variation in anatomy, pathology, and surgical conditions. The synthetic data is designed to reflect a wide range of clinically relevant scenarios encountered in retinal surgery, ensuring diversity in simulated patient characteristics, disease presentations, and procedural complexity. This approach allows participants to develop and evaluate algorithms in a reproducible setting while targeting real-world clinical applications in multimodal ophthalmic surgery. Although the core dataset is synthetic, the testing phase incorporates 100 real-world data samples to evaluate the algorithms' capability in adapting to domain shifts.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The dataset includes surgical microscope fundus imaging, which provides a wide-field en face view of the surgical scene, and intraoperative Optical Coherence Tomography (iOCT), which offers high-resolution cross-sectional anatomical information over a localized region of interest. These complementary imaging modalities are provided in a synchronized manner to enable the development and evaluation of algorithms for multimodal image fusion.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

In addition to the image data, the challenge provides rich auxiliary annotations and metadata directly related to the imaging content. These include keypoints of surgical instruments fundus images, as well as in the iOCT slices. Furthermore, the dataset includes quantitative measurements of tool-tissue distance, and the spatial transformation parameters between the iOCT slices and corresponding fundus images. Information describing the rotation and pose of the eye is also provided.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information is available related to patients.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

While no data is directly acquired from patients during the challenge, the synthetic images are modeled based on real clinical cases and surgical scenarios obtained from partner university clinics. The synthetic dataset (which has been verified in terms of realism by clinical experts) realistically represents retinal anatomy, surgical instruments, eye motion, and intraoperative conditions across both fundus and iOCT modalities, ensuring relevance to the intended real-world retinal surgery application while avoiding the use of identifiable patient data. Test-phase real data is sourced from partner university clinics under their authorization and specific patient consents. These images are acquired using hardware specifications consistent with the challenge's synthetic data characteristics.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithms in the first task of the challenge are designed to target the spatial localization of surgical tool keypoints. Participating methods are expected to leverage multimodal intraoperative imaging by fusing information from the provided modalities, each of which contributes complementary cues that cannot be fully captured by the other alone. As a result, accurate keypoint localization relies on the joint interpretation of both imaging sources.

The challenge explicitly evaluates the ability of algorithms to utilize multimodal information. In addition to standard performance assessment, modality-specific ablation is conducted to analyze algorithm behavior when one modality is absent, thereby encouraging robust multimodal designs. Furthermore, participants may explore approaches in which one modality is used as a supervisory signal to guide the training of models operating on the other modality, promoting effective cross-modal learning.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Precision,Robustness,Runtime,Reliability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The challenge data consists of synthetic multimodal retinal surgery data generated by SynthesEyes GmbH. While no physical imaging devices were used to acquire the data, the synthetic dataset is modeled on real surgical cases and imaging characteristics from partner university clinics, including the appearance and properties of fundus

microscope images and intraoperative OCT (iOCT) slices.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The challenge dataset consists of synthetic data provided by SynthesEyes GmbH, generated based on clinical cases supplied by partner university clinics.

The synthetic fundus microscope images are modeled to replicate the characteristics of ZEISS surgical microscopes, including field of view, illumination, and optical properties.

Moreover, the synthetic iOCT simulate high-resolution, cross-sectional, and volumetric imaging of retinal layers, modeled to replicate the characteristics of ZEISS intraoperative OCT systems.

The simulated surgical procedures, including tool motion, tool-tissue interaction and eye rotations, are performed by professionals and verified by senior surgeons to ensure clinical accuracy. Together, the fundus and iOCT modalities provide a clinically realistic multimodal dataset suitable for developing and evaluating algorithms for tool localization, tool-tissue distance estimation, and multimodal data fusion, without using identifiable patient data.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The clinical data used to generate the synthetic dataset was provided by the Rotterdam Ophthalmic Institute (R.O.I.). SynthesEyes GmbH utilized this data to create the multimodal synthetic dataset. Additionally, Carl Zeiss Meditec AG supplied detailed specifications of their surgical microscopes and iOCT systems to ensure that the simulations accurately reflect real-world imaging conditions.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The creation of the dataset involved a team of highly experienced professionals to ensure clinical and technical realism. This includes one renowned expert retina surgeon, a professor specializing in Computer-Aided Medical Procedures, and industry professionals in the ophthalmic and eye-care sector. Their combined expertise guided both the modeling of surgical procedures and the design of the multimodal imaging simulations.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each case includes synchronized multimodal data, specifically: fundus microscope video frames and corresponding synthetic iOCT slices, along with annotations such as tool keypoints, tool-tissue distances, and

spatial transformations between modalities.

Each case represents a surgical scenario, including the dynamics of surgical tools and eye motion during epiretinal membrane peeling or subretinal injection. To ensure diversity and clinical relevance, each case features a unique setting, varying in lighting conditions, pathology, patient anatomy or surgical maneuver. The dataset consists of 30 cases, with 25 for training, 5 for validation (and 5 for testing, which are not released). Each video is approximately 1 minute long at 15 fps, resulting in roughly 1,000 frames per video. This design provides a comprehensive and variable dataset suitable for developing and evaluating multimodal fusion algorithms in retinal surgery.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 25 videos ~25,000 frames

Validation: 5 videos ~5,000 frames

Testing: 5 videos ~5,000 frames and ~100 Samples of real-world data with higher weight.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

This split balances clinical variability, algorithm development needs, and computational feasibility:

- Training (25 cases): These 25 cases are designed to cover a wide range of variability in anatomy, pathology, lighting, and surgical conditions. If a model cannot generalize after training on these cases, the limitation lies with the method, not the data. This ensures that the challenge evaluates algorithmic robustness rather than dataset coverage.
- Validation (5 cases): Provides an independent set for hyperparameter tuning and performance monitoring, allowing participants to assess generalization without overfitting.
- Test (5 cases, unreleased): Ensures a fair and unbiased evaluation, representing diverse scenarios not seen during training, including variations in patient anatomy, pathology, and imaging conditions.
- Test (~100 real-world data, unreleased): Testing algorithms trained solely on synthetic data against real-world data emphasizes the generalization capabilities and clinical robustness of those models. Since collecting and annotating such data requires considerable effort, this portion will be assigned a higher weight in the final evaluation metric to prioritize models that successfully bridge the sim-to-real gap.

This configuration provides a clinically meaningful, diverse, and computationally tractable dataset for developing and benchmarking multimodal algorithms in retinal surgery, emphasizing methodological innovation and generalization over data quantity.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The annotated dataset is entirely new unseen and unpublished data. The annotations for the final evaluation set will be not shared with challenge participants.

Each fundus image is a 1024x1024 RGB image, and each iOCT Cross Section is a 512x512 greyscale image. There are two iOCT slices provided per frame. The exact dimensions will be announced upon dataset release and are subject to change.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The challenge will use entirely new, previously unseen, and unpublished data. SynthesEyes GmbH, in collaboration with ZEISS, is releasing this unique multimodal retinal surgery dataset for the first time as part of this challenge. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first fully annotated dataset of retinal surgical procedures combining fundus microscope imaging and intraoperative OCT (iOCT).

All cases included in the challenge are newly released and have not been used in any prior public benchmarks. While the underlying synthetic data generation framework has been validated and its impact demonstrated through prior publications in top-tier venues (e.g., MICCAI, IEEE TMI, Scientific Reports, Medical Image Analysis), the dataset itself has not been previously available to the research community.

By releasing this dataset through the challenge, we aim to enable broader exploration of multimodal data fusion in retinal surgery and to stimulate further methodological advances with significant clinical and scientific impact.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Since the dataset is fully synthetic, annotations such as surgical tool keypoints, tool-tissue distances, and multimodal spatial transformations are generated directly from the underlying simulation models and are therefore inherently accurate.

To ensure clinical validity and realism, both the synthetic generation methods and the resulting annotations have been reviewed and validated by experienced clinicians. This process is applied consistently across the training, validation, and test sets. No manual image annotation by human annotators was required.

The real-world test set were manually annotated by clinical experts with extensive experience in ophthalmic surgery.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not relevant.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The dataset consists of synthetic data, which by design has accurate annotations. To ensure clinical validity and realism, clinicians have been involved in reviewing the data. In addition, the methods used to model and generate the synthetic data, including the algorithms and models created by SynthesEyes GmbH, have been validated by clinicians, confirming that both the generation process and the resulting data accurately reflect real intraoperative retinal surgery scenarios.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not relevant.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not relevant.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Not relevant.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Not relevant.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Algorithm performance is primarily assessed using the AUC (Area Under the Curve) of the Euclidean distance of the predicted and reference surgical tool keypoints. While keypoints can be interpreted in three dimensions, combining X-Y localization from fundus images and depth from iOCT, a single Euclidean distance metric is used to provide a consistent evaluation across modalities.

To evaluate the effectiveness of data fusion, some test cases are evaluated with only one modality available (i.e., either fundus or iOCT is withheld), testing the algorithm's ability to generalize and leverage the remaining

modality effectively.

To evaluate the algorithms' potential for clinical translation, they are benchmarked against a real-world test set. The evaluation metrics for this subset are weighted to ensure a balanced comparison.

Algorithms are ranked based on the mentioned metric over the test cases. Algorithms whose inference time in a test case exceeds the specified maximum limit are disregarded and would receive a 0 for that test case.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The Euclidean distance error was chosen as the primary metric because accurate spatial localization of surgical tool keypoints is critical in vitreoretinal surgery, where sub-millimeter precision directly impacts patient safety and surgical outcomes. This metric provides an intuitive and clinically meaningful measure of localization accuracy that is independent of imaging modality, allowing consistent evaluation when combining fundus and iOCT information. To summarize performance across different levels of precision, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Euclidean distance error is used, providing a single scalar value that reflects both accuracy and robustness of keypoint localization.

The inclusion of modality ablation-based robustness assessment reflects realistic intraoperative conditions, where one imaging modality may be intermittently unavailable. Evaluating performance degradation under ablation ensures that algorithms are not only accurate when full multimodal data is present, but also reliable and resilient in practical surgical settings.

Finally, enforcing a maximum inference time per test case ensures that algorithms are suitable for real-time intraoperative workflows, supporting timely surgical decision-making without introducing delays. Algorithms exceeding this limit receive a penalized score, emphasizing the clinical requirement for both accuracy and computational efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The steps are as follows:

1- Per Test Case Evaluation:

- Compute the Euclidean distance error between each predicted keypoint and its ground-truth location.
- Calculate the AUC of the Euclidean distance error up to a specified threshold.

2- Modality Ablation Assessment:

- Some test cases may include only one imaging modality (fundus or iOCT) to reflect realistic intraoperative conditions.
- Compute the AUC separately for these ablated cases to evaluate algorithm performance when multimodal data is partially unavailable.

3- Inference Time Penalty:

- If an algorithm's inference time for a test case exceeds the maximum allowed, assign a fixed penalized score, 0, for that case.

4- Weighted Aggregation Across Test Cases:

- Compute the mean AUC across all test cases (full and ablated) to obtain an overall performance score. The results from the synthetic test set and real test set will be weighted differently to prioritize clinical relevance and reward models that successfully bridge the sim-to-real gap.

5- Ranking:

- Algorithms are ranked in descending order of mean AUC (higher is better).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Incomplete submissions or submissions missing results will be disqualified. If an algorithm's inference time for a test case exceeds the maximum allowed or fails to produce a valid result, assign a fixed penalized score, 0, for that test case. The exact GPU model and inference speed threshold will be announced.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The described ranking scheme was chosen to provide a comprehensive and clinically relevant evaluation of surgical tool keypoint localization algorithms. Computing the Euclidean distance error and summarizing it with the AUC captures both the accuracy and robustness of localization across varying precision thresholds, which is critical for vitreoretinal surgery where sub-millimeter errors can impact patient safety and surgical outcomes.

Including modality ablation cases ensures that algorithms are evaluated not only under ideal multimodal conditions but also under realistic intraoperative scenarios where one imaging modality may be intermittently unavailable.

Applying a penalized score for exceeding inference time enforces the requirement for real-time applicability, ensuring that high accuracy is paired with computational efficiency.

Finally, aggregating performance across all test cases and ranking by mean AUC provides a single interpretable measure that balances precision, robustness, and practical feasibility. By applying a higher weight to the real-world test results, the final ranking specifically highlights algorithms that demonstrate the highest potential for clinical translation.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Algorithm performance is evaluated on all test cases using the primary metric (AUC of Euclidean distance or corner error). To account for variability across test cases, bootstrap resampling is performed: metrics are recomputed for each algorithm on resampled test sets, and algorithms are ranked within each iteration. The

mean rank across all iterations defines the preliminary ranking, ensuring that algorithms with consistent performance are prioritized. To ensure that final rankings reflect meaningful differences rather than stochastic noise, paired t-tests are performed between consecutively ranked algorithms over the full test set. Algorithms without a statistically significant difference are assigned the same rank.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of each algorithm's performance is measured using confidence intervals from bootstrap resampling. For each algorithm, the performance metric is recalculated on multiple resampled test sets, and the percentile range of these results defines the confidence interval. This shows the certainty about the algorithm's average performance.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Variability of algorithm performance across test cases is assessed using bootstrap resampling of the test set.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

For each bootstrap replicate of the test set, algorithms are ranked based on their metric values. The distribution of ranks across all bootstrap iterations captures how sensitive each algorithm's relative position is to variations in the test cases.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Paired t-tests on per-test-case metric values are used to determine whether performance differences between consecutively ranked algorithms are statistically significant. Algorithms without a significant difference ($p > 0.05$) are assigned the same rank.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

All frames and corresponding annotations are fully available in the synthetic dataset, so no missing data imputation is required for the test case. In the event of a crash or if a test case exceeds the maximum allowed inference time, the corresponding data is handled by assigning a fixed penalty error (0 for both tasks) to ensure that the algorithm is fairly included in the performance evaluation while reflecting the failure to produce timely results.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All data aggregation, metric computation, and statistical analyses will be performed using Python (NumPy, Pandas) and standard scientific computing libraries.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or

- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 2: Intraoperative iOCT to Fundus registration

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

When multiple imaging modalities are used simultaneously, accurate knowledge of the transformation between them becomes critical for applications such as manual surgical guidance, computer-assisted decision support, and robotic task autonomy. In practice, this alignment is typically achieved through hardware-based calibration of the medical devices. However, such calibrations may become inaccurate or outdated due to factors such as dynamic optical changes or inherent hardware limitations. As a result, an additional computational refinement step is often required to improve cross-modal alignment.

In this task, the objective is to estimate the transformation matrix that accurately aligns the volumetric iOCT data with the corresponding microscope fundus image, thereby correcting residual miscalibration and ensuring precise multimodal and rigid registration while maintaining high inference speed suitable for real-time intraoperative use. Notably, this registration is a 3D-to-2D problem, involving alignment between volumetric OCT data and 2D microscope images.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multi-modal calibration, Multi-modal image fusion

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Shervin Dehghani (1),

Michael Sommersperger (1),

Christian Kungel (3),

Ghazal Ghazaei (2, 4),

Hendrik Burwinkel (3),

Koorosh Faridpooya (5)

Nassir Navab (4)

–

(1) SynthesEyes GmbH, Munich, DE

(2) Corporate Research and Technology, Carl Zeiss AG, Munich, DE

(3) Advanced Development, Carl Zeiss Meditec AG, Munich, DE

(4) Chair of Computer Aided Medical Procedures (CAMP), Technical University of Munich (TUM)

(5) Rotterdam Eye Hospital, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Michael Sommersperger (SynthesEyes GmbH)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Similar to Task 1.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention 2026 (MICCAI)

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Will be hosted on codabench.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

All relevant information about the challenge, including key details such as deadlines, submission instructions, and evaluation criteria, along with all relevant links, will be made available on the official challenge website. This website is hosted by SynthesEyes GmbH and will serve as the central hub for participants to stay updated on all aspects of the challenge.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

There are no restrictions on the data that can be used for training. While the necessary training data will be provided and the evaluation dataset will be similar in nature, researchers are encouraged to leverage additional publicly available datasets and pre-trained models. Any such additional data or models used must be clearly documented, specifying which datasets and pre-trained networks were incorporated into the training process.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top-performing team in the qualitative evaluation and the team with the most innovative or impactful approach will receive awards. The award amounts will be announced later.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top performing team of the task will be announced publicly on the challenge website.

Moreover, the team with the most innovative or impactful approach for the task will be announced publicly on the challenge website.

All these teams will be listed as co-authors in the final manuscript, and have the opportunity to present their method on the challenge day.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Same as Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Same as Task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Same as Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Same as Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Not applicable to our dataset, since it is purely synthetic. While the evaluation phase incorporates real-world data to test for domain shift, this specific subset will remain private and will not be released for public distribution.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide the corresponding links for the data loaders and evaluation code to participants of the challenge. This release is planned for the beginning of May 2026.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Same as Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Same as Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Surgery,Assistance,Intervention planning,Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection

- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Calibration,Registration

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 1.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Same as Task 1.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The dataset includes surgical microscope fundus imaging, similar to Task 1, which provides a wide-field fundus view of the surgical scene, and intraoperative Optical Coherence Tomography (iOCT) volumes, unlike task 1 which is only slices. These complementary imaging modalities are provided in a synchronized manner to enable the development and evaluation of algorithms for multimodal calibration.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Similar to Task 1, this task differs in that a full iOCT volume is provided, and the transformation that maps the volume to the corresponding fundus image is provided. Moreover, to give participants additional guidance for algorithm development, vessel segmentations and retinal layer masks are provided for both the fundus images and the iOCT volume.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information is available related to patients.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The second task focuses on calibrating the two imaging modalities: the fundus image and the volumetric iOCT.

The challenge assesses algorithms' ability to determine a common intermediate space between the modalities and accurately estimate the transformation parameters in real time. Inference time constraints are imposed to encourage the development of methods capable of efficient 3D data processing suitable for intraoperative use.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Runtime, Precision, Robustness

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The challenge data consists of synthetic multimodal retinal surgery data generated by SynthesEyes GmbH. While no physical imaging devices were used to acquire the data, the synthetic dataset is modeled on real surgical cases and imaging characteristics from partner university clinics, including the appearance and properties of fundus microscope images and intraoperative OCT (iOCT) volumes.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Same as Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Same as Task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Same as Task 1.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each case represents a snapshot of a surgical scenario, including synchronized multimodal data, specifically: fundus microscope image and corresponding synthetic iOCT volume, along with anatomical annotations and spatial transformations between modalities.

To ensure diversity and clinical relevance, cases feature various settings, varying in lighting conditions, pathology, patient anatomy or surgical manuvre. The dataset consists of 180 cases, with 150 for training, 30 for validation (and 30 for testing, which are not released).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 150 snapshots => 150 iOCT Volumes + 150 Fundus images

Validation: 30 snapshots => 30 iOCT Volumes + 30 Fundus images

Testing: 30 snapshots => 30 iOCT Volumes + 30 Fundus images and 10 real-world data with higher weight.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

This configuration provides a clinically meaningful, diverse, and computationally tractable dataset for developing and benchmarking multimodal algorithms in retinal surgery, emphasizing methodological innovation and generalization over data quantity.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The annotated dataset is entirely new unseen and unpublished data. The annotations for the final evaluation set will be not shared with challenge participants.

Each fundus image has a 1024x1024 RGB image, and each iOCT Volume is a 512x256x256 greyscale volume, which is provided in 256 slices of 256x256 greyscale images. The exact dimensions will be announced upon dataset release and are subject to change.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Same as Task 1.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Similar to Task 1.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not relevant.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Similar to Task 1.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not relevant.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not relevant.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Not relevant.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Not relevant.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The primary metric for Task 2 is the AUC (Area Under the Curve) of the corner error, which quantifies the accuracy of mapping 3D iOCT points to 2D fundus image coordinates. The corner error for each point is defined as the Euclidean distance between the predicted 2D location, obtained by applying the algorithm's estimated transformation to a 3D iOCT point, and the corresponding ground-truth 2D point. The AUC is calculated as the area under the cumulative error distribution curve up to a specified threshold, providing a single measure that reflects both the precision and robustness of the 3D-to-2D alignment.

To evaluate the algorithms' potential for clinical translation, they are benchmarked against a real-world test set. The evaluation metrics for this subset are weighted to ensure a balanced comparison,

Algorithms are ranked based on the mentioned metric over the test cases. Algorithms whose inference time in a test case exceeds the specified maximum limit are disregarded and would receive a 0 for that test case.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The AUC of the corner error was chosen as the primary metric because it directly quantifies the accuracy of mapping 3D iOCT points to 2D fundus image coordinates, which is critical for intraoperative guidance and surgical decision support. Accurate 3D-to-2D registration ensures that volumetric OCT information can be correctly overlaid on the fundus image, enabling precise interpretation of retinal structures, surgical tool positions, and critical anatomical landmarks during vitreoretinal procedures.

Using the AUC provides a single summary measure that reflects performance across a range of error thresholds, capturing both the precision and robustness of the registration. This is particularly important in surgical applications, where consistent performance across varying anatomical structures and imaging conditions is essential for patient safety.

Finally, enforcing a maximum inference time per test case ensures that algorithms are suitable for real-time intraoperative workflows, supporting timely surgical decision-making without introducing delays. Algorithms exceeding this limit receive a penalized score, emphasizing the clinical requirement for both accuracy and computational efficiency.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The steps are as follows:

1- Per Test Case Evaluation:

- Compute the corner error for each 3D iOCT point: the Euclidean distance between the predicted 2D location and the ground-truth 2D point.
- Generate the cumulative error distribution and calculate the AUC of the corner error up to a specified threshold.

2- Inference Time Penalty:

- If an algorithm's inference time for a test case exceeds the maximum allowed, assign a fixed penalized score, 0, for that test case.

3- Weighted Aggregation Across Test Cases:

- Compute the mean AUC across all test cases to obtain a single overall score for the algorithm. The results from the synthetic test set and real test set will be weighted differently to prioritize clinical relevance and reward models that successfully bridge the sim-to-real gap.

4- Ranking:

- Rank algorithms in descending order of mean AUC (higher is better).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Same as task 1.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The described ranking scheme was chosen to ensure that algorithms are evaluated both accurately and practically for intraoperative use. Computing the corner error and summarizing it via the AUC directly reflects the algorithm's ability to map 3D iOCT points to 2D fundus coordinates with precision, which is critical for real-time guidance in vitreoretinal surgery where sub-millimeter localization errors can affect patient safety and surgical outcomes.

Applying an inference time penalty ensures that algorithms not only achieve high accuracy but are also computationally efficient, meeting the clinical requirement for real-time applicability.

Finally, aggregating performance across multiple test cases by taking the mean AUC captures both accuracy and consistency across diverse anatomical structures and imaging conditions. By applying a higher weight to the real-world test results, the final ranking specifically highlights algorithms that demonstrate the highest potential for clinical translation.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Similar to Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Same as task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Similar to task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Similar to Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A